

Supplementary Materials

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3 **Role of diesel exhaust particle-induced cellular senescence in the**
4 **development of asthma in young and old mice**

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6 Hyun-Seung Lee, PhD¹, Heung-Woo Park, MD, PhD^{2,3}

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8 ¹Biomedical Research Institute, Seoul National University Hospital, Seoul, Korea

9 ²Department of Internal Medicine, Seoul National University Hospital, Seoul, Republic
10 of Korea

11 ³Department of Internal Medicine, Seoul National University College of Medicine,
12 Seoul, Republic of Korea

13 **SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE LEGENDS**

14 **Figure S1. DEP-induced cellular senescence in mice lungs**

15 A. Experimental protocol. B. Inflammatory cells in the bronchoalveolar lavage fluid. C.
16 SA- β -gal activity in the lung homogenate. The Y axis represents the relative
17 fluorescence unit (RFU). D. S100A8/9 level in the bronchoalveolar lavage fluid. E.
18 Gating plots and frequency of the CD45⁺EpCAM⁺ population in the S100A8/9⁺p-
19 mTOR⁺ cells of the lung tissue.

20 Five to six mice were used per group. Results are presented as the mean \pm standard
21 deviation. [#] $P < 0.05$, ^{##} $P < 0.01$ compared to the PBS group. Statistical analysis was
22 performed using a one-way analysis of variance with Bonferroni's multiple
23 comparisons. DEP, diesel exhaust particle; PBS, phosphate-buffered saline; SA- β -
24 gal, senescence-associated beta-galactosidase

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26 **Figure S2. Effects of m-TOR signal inhibition on DEP-induced changes in the**
27 **CD45⁺CD4⁺ and CD45⁺CD11c⁺ cells of the lung tissue**

28 A. Gating plots and frequency of the SA- β -gal⁺CD4⁺ population in the CD45⁺ cells of
29 the lung tissue. B. Gating plots and frequency of the SA- β -gal⁺CD11c⁺ population in the
30 CD45⁺ cells of the lung tissue. C. Gating plots and frequency of the S100A8/9⁺CD4⁺
31 population in the CD45⁺ cells of the lung tissue. D. Gating plots and frequency of the
32 S100A8/9⁺CD11c⁺ population in the CD45⁺ cells of the lung tissue. E. Gating plots and
33 frequency of the HMGB1⁺CD4⁺ population in the CD45⁺ cells of the lung tissue. F.
34 Gating plots and frequency of the HMGB1⁺CD11c⁺ population in the CD45⁺ cells of the
35 lung tissue.

36 Five to six mice were used per group. Results are presented as the mean \pm standard

37 deviation. #*P* < 0.05, ##*P* < 0.01 compared to the PBS group. Statistical analysis was
38 performed using a one-way analysis of variance with Bonferroni's multiple
39 comparisons. DEP, diesel exhaust particle; PBS, phosphate-buffered saline; SA-β-
40 gal, senescence-associated beta-galactosidase

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42 **Figure S3. Gating strategies of immune cells**

43 A. Acquired immune cells (Th1, Th2, and Th17 T cells). B. Innate immune cells (ILC1,
44 ILC2, and ILC3)

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46 **Figure S4. IL-33, TSLP, and IL-1β levels in the lung homogenate before DEP** 47 **instillation**

48 A. Young mice. B. Old mice.

49 Five to six mice were used per group. Results are presented as the mean ± standard
50 deviation. #*P* < 0.05 compared to PBS group. Statistical analysis was performed using a
51 one-way analysis of variance with Bonferroni's multiple comparisons. PBS, phosphate-
52 buffered saline; DEP, diesel exhaust particle; TSLP, thymic stromal lymphopietin.

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54 **Figure S5. Effects of rapamycin on the DEP-stimulated A549 cells**

55 Frequency of the S100A8/9⁺p-mTOR⁺ population in the DEP-stimulated A549 cells
56 (with or without rapamycin). The experiments were repeated three times and showed
57 similar results; thus a representative result is presented. Results are presented as the
58 mean ± standard deviation. #*P* < 0.05, ##*P* < 0.01 compared to the media only group. **P* <
59 0.05, ***P* < 0.01, between two groups. Statistical analysis was performed using a one-
60 way analysis of variance with Bonferroni's multiple comparisons. DEP, diesel exhaust

61 particle

62 **Table S1. List of antibodies for flow cytometry**

Product	Company	Clone	Order number	Dilution factor
CD45	Invitrogen	30-F11	45-0451-80	1:200
EpCAM	Biolegend	G8.8	118225	1:200
p-mTOR	Invitrogen	MRRBY	25-9718-42	1:200
S100A8/9	Novus Biologicals	MAC387	NBP2-47667F	1:100
SA- β -gal	Invitrogen		C10840	1:200
CD4	Biolegend	RM4-5	100557	1:200
CD11c	BD	HL3	561241	1:100
F4/80	Invitrogen	BM8	69-4801-80	1:100
HMGB1	Biolegend	3E8	651404	1:200
cd11c	Biolegend	N418	117306	1:100
cd11b	Biolegend	M1/70	101206	1:100
Fc ϵ RIa	Biolegend	01-Mar	134305	1:100
CD19	Biolegend	6D5	115506	1:100
CD49	Invitrogen	DX5	11-5971-82	1:100
CD3e	Invitrogen	145-2C11	11-0031-82	1:100
F4/80	eBioscience	BM8	11-4801-85	1:200
CD4	Biolegend	RM4-5	100557	1:200
IL-17	Biolegend	TC11-18H10.1	506926	1:100
ST2	Biolegend	DIH9	145311	1:100
IL-7R	Biolegend	A7R34	135041	1:50
IFN- γ	BD Biosciences	XMG1.2	554412	1:100
IL-5	BD Biosciences	TRFK5	554396	1:100
IL-13	Invitrogen	eBio13A	25-7133-82	1:100
MHCII	Invitrogen	AMS-32.1	17-5323-80	1:250
HLA-DR	Invitrogen	LN3	25-9956-42	1:200

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65 # Isotype Ab

Product	Company	Clone	Order number	Dilution factor
FITC Armenian Hamster IgG Isotype Control	Biolegend	HTK888	400905	1:1000
FITC Rat IgG2b, κ Isotype Control	Biolegend	RTK4530	400633	1:1000
Rat IgM Isotype Control, FITC	Invitrogen	eBRM	11-4341-82	1:1000
Brilliant Violet 605™ Rat IgG2a, κ Isotype Control	Biolegend	RTK2758	400539	1:500
Brilliant Violet 421™ Rat IgG1, κ Isotype Control	Biolegend	RTK2071	400429	1:500
Mouse IgG2b κ Isotype Control, PE-Cy7	Invitrogen	eBMG2b	25-4732-81	1:1000
Mouse IgG2a κ Isotype Control, PE-Cy7	Invitrogen	eBM2a	25-4724-81	1:500
Rat IgG1 κ Isotype Control, PE-Cyanine7	Invitrogen	eBRG1	25-4301-82	1:1000
APC Rat IgG1, κ Isotype Control	BD Biosciences	R3-34	554686	1:500
PE Rat IgG1, κ Isotype Control	BD Biosciences	R3-34	554685	1:1000
Mouse IgG1 Isotype Control	Novus Biologicals	11711	IC002G	1:1000
PerCP/Cyanine5.5 Rat IgG2a, κ Isotype Control	Biolegend	RTK2758	400531	1:1000
PE Mouse IgG2b, κ Isotype Control	Biolegend	MPC-11	400311	1:1000

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70 **Figure S1.**

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